

Unveiling the Value Proposition: Real Estate Appraisers as Strategic Partners in Business Decision-Making

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the role of real estate appraisers in strategic decision-making and value enhancement, focusing on planning aspects often overlooked in existing literature. With Saudi Arabia's rapid real estate market growth and increased competition among valuation companies, there is a need for a deeper understanding of the appraisal process and its strategic implications. The study uses a descriptive approach to examine literature reviews, focusing on the establishment of the Saudi Authority for Accredited Valuers (TAQEEM) in 2017. It highlights the strategic significance of real estate appraisers in navigating the complexities of the valuation process and driving value creation for businesses. The study also highlights the multifaceted roles of appraisers in risk management, financial reporting, investment analysis, portfolio management, and market intelligence. It also explores the implications of technological integration in appraisal practices and offers actionable recommendations for maximizing appraiser contributions to business strategy.

INTRODUCTION

The real estate sector plays a crucial role in driving both domestic growth and the global economy. The global real estate market is poised to achieve an impressive value of US\$637.80 trillion by 2024 (Statista Market Insights, 2024a). Within this expansive market, residential real estate stands out as the dominant segment, projected to reach a market volume of US\$518.90 trillion in the same year. Looking forward, the sector is expected to maintain a steady growth trajectory, with an anticipated annual growth rate of 3.41% (CAGR 2024-2028), culminating in a market volume of US\$729.40 trillion by 2028.

In Saudi Arabia, the real estate sector holds a prominent position of paramount importance compared to other economic sectors. The rapid urbanization witnessed not only in Saudi Arabia but also globally is attributed to several factors, namely population growth, governmental policies and regulations, and economic mobility. These three factors consistently emerge as the primary drivers behind the significant expansion of cities worldwide, with Saudi Arabia experiencing notable growth in this regard. The Saudi Arabian real estate market is forecasted to achieve a value of US\$2.10 trillion by 2024 (Statista Market Insights, 2024b). Leading the market segments, residential real estate commands the largest share, expected to attain a market volume of US\$1.43 trillion in 2024. Projections suggest this segment will maintain a steady growth trajectory, with an estimated annual growth rate of 2.96% from 2024 to 2028, culminating in a market volume of US\$2.36 trillion by 2028. The surge in demand for luxury properties in Saudi Arabia can be attributed to the burgeoning affluent population within the country.

This disparity underscores the paramount importance of the real estate industry. Among the crucial factors shaping the efficacy of real estate operations, property valuation stands out prominently. Precise valuation by appraisers is imperative, as inaccuracies in assessments can significantly impact various stakeholders, including governments, policymakers, financial institutions, investors, insurance agencies, real estate developers, and the general public (Abidoye et al., 2019; Vo, 2014; Wang et al., 2019). Clients typically seek cost-effective valuation services, prompting a proactive embrace of automation within the valuation process (Elliott and Warren, 2011). Moreover, the proliferation of freely available data has democratized access to property information, challenging the traditional exclusivity of real estate specialists' data access and thereby complicating their profession (Abidoye et al., 2019; Wilkinson et al., 2018). Inherent characteristics of the real estate valuation process, such as immovability, durability, and its heavy reliance on property attributes and geographical factors, naturally add complexity to estimations (Li and Monkkonen, 2014). Furthermore, economic indicators, heterogeneity, and stakeholder behaviors are additional variables influencing real estate prices (Baldominos et al., 2018). Consequently, when dealing with numerous properties boasting diverse features, valuation professionals encounter challenges in effectively managing such vast amounts of data and factors. To address these complexities, reliable, efficient, and innovative

automated valuation models (AVMs) are indispensable (Jahanshiri et al., 2011; Metzner and Kindt, 2017; Božić et al., 2013). Deploying such advanced models is crucial for ensuring accuracy and efficiency in real estate valuation processes, particularly in the face of multifaceted data and variables. The burgeoning activity in the real estate market has attracted a multitude of individuals and institutions, leading to a surge in companies interested in real estate valuation and assessment processes. This heightened activity prompted the establishment of the Saudi Authority for Accredited Valuers. However, despite the rapid pace of real estate transactions in Saudi Arabia, a critical aspect of the sector has been overlooked: the lack of comprehensive scientific studies and methodologies for real estate valuation, particularly from the perspectives of urban planning and architecture. Most existing studies have predominantly focused on the financial aspects, neglecting crucial considerations related to urban and architectural planning.

Presently, the evaluation process and real estate valuation in Saudi Arabia rely heavily on experience and subjective opinions, which can be subject to fair criticism and skepticism. Moreover, the continued reliance on traditional valuation methods, despite the inherent complexities of urban planning and architectural structures, raises questions about the efficacy of the valuation process. Furthermore, the absence of a standardized professional framework for real estate evaluation in Saudi Arabia compounds the challenges, as there is no universally recognized set of procedures or criteria that accredited individuals can follow when assessing properties. Consequently, the valuation and assessment process become cumbersome, requiring extensive experience and in-depth knowledge. Enhancing the professionalism and transparency of the evaluation industry is essential to instill confidence among financiers, investors, and buyers in the market. Establishing clear professional standards and guidelines for real estate valuation would ensure a neutral and transparent assessment of property prices, fostering trust and fairness in the market (Al-Jarallah and Alkadi, 2017).

This paper aims to explore the strategic importance of real estate appraisers for businesses, shedding light on their multifaceted contributions to various aspects of corporate operations and decision-making. By synthesizing existing literature, theoretical support, and industry insights, it seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how real estate appraisers facilitate value creation, risk mitigation, and strategic alignment in business contexts. Additionally, the paper aims to identify emerging trends and challenges shaping the role of appraisers and offer practical recommendations for businesses to leverage their expertise effectively. Understanding the strategic significance of real estate appraisers is crucial for businesses across industries. Effective real estate asset management and decision-making require accurate valuation, informed analysis, and proactive risk management, all of which are facilitated by skilled appraisers. By recognizing the value of real estate appraisers and leveraging their expertise, businesses can enhance their competitive positioning, optimize resource allocation, and capitalize on opportunities in the dynamic real estate market. Moreover, insights from this

paper can inform policy discussions, educational curricula, and professional development initiatives aimed at strengthening the appraisal profession and promoting sustainable real estate practices.

The paper's structure unfolds as follows: After this introduction, it progresses to provide a theoretical framework for understanding the role of real estate appraisers in business strategy. Subsequently, it explores the strategic functions of appraisers, encompassing risk management, financial reporting, investment analysis, portfolio management, and market intelligence. The paper then examines the contribution of real estate appraisers to organizational agility and resilience. Following this, it discusses the integration of technology in real estate appraisal and its implications. The paper proceeds to highlight future directions and implications, concluding with a summary of key findings and offering final remarks.

Saudi Authority for Accredited Valuers (TAQEEM)

The Saudi Authority for Accredited Valuers (TAQEEM) [<https://taqem.gov.sa/en/>] is a pivotal institution within the Saudi Arabian real estate landscape, established with the aim of regulating and standardizing the valuation process. Founded in early 2017, TAQEEM plays a crucial role in organizing and overseeing the real estate valuation sector in the Kingdom. TAQEEM's primary objective is to ensure transparency, professionalism, and reliability in real estate valuation practices. It achieves this by setting rigorous standards, guidelines, and codes of conduct for accredited valuers, thereby instilling confidence and trust in the valuation process among stakeholders.

One of TAQEEM's key functions is the accreditation and certification of real estate valuation professionals. By establishing criteria for accreditation and conducting rigorous assessments, TAQEEM ensures that only qualified and competent individuals are authorized to perform valuations, thus raising the overall standard of valuation services in the Kingdom. Moreover, TAQEEM serves as a platform for knowledge-sharing and professional development within the real estate valuation community. It facilitates training programs, workshops, and conferences aimed at enhancing the skills and competencies of valuers, keeping them abreast of emerging trends, technologies, and best practices in the field.

In addition to its regulatory and educational roles, TAQEEM acts as a central repository of real estate valuation data and information. By collecting, analyzing, and disseminating market data, TAQEEM provides valuable insights into market trends, property values, and investment opportunities, thereby supporting informed decision-making by investors, policymakers, and other stakeholders.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this study adopts a descriptive approach to analyze literature reviews concerning the pivotal role of real estate appraisers in strategic decision-making and value enhancement, with a specific emphasis on the planning aspects often overlooked in existing research. To begin, a

thorough literature review is conducted, spanning academic databases, journals, conference proceedings, and reputable sources in the field of real estate and appraisal. This review aims to identify relevant studies, articles, and scholarly publications that shed light on real estate valuation, appraiser roles, strategic decision-making, and value creation, particularly within the context of businesses. Selection criteria are predefined, encompassing factors such as relevance to the study objectives, publication date, academic rigor, and applicability to the Saudi Arabian real estate market context.

Subsequently, pertinent information and findings are extracted from the selected literature and organized systematically. This process involves synthesizing insights into the strategic importance of real estate appraisers, their roles in decision-making processes, value creation strategies, and the implications of planning aspects in the valuation process. The extracted data is then analyzed thematically to identify recurring themes, patterns, and insights relevant to the study objectives. Special attention is given to the planning dimensions of real estate valuation and appraiser contributions to strategic decision-making and value enhancement.

Following the analysis, the synthesized findings are interpreted to develop a coherent narrative that elucidates the strategic significance of real estate appraisers in businesses, particularly within the Saudi Arabian real estate market context. The interpretation integrates theoretical support, empirical evidence, and industry insights to provide a holistic understanding of the appraisal process and its implications for strategic management. Ultimately, the study aims to offer actionable recommendations for maximizing appraiser contributions to strategic decision-making and value creation in the dynamic real estate landscape. Through this methodology, rigor and relevance are ensured in analyzing literature reviews and synthesizing insights into the strategic importance of real estate appraisers in businesses.

RESEARCH RESULT

Resource-Based View (RBV) Perspective: The Resource-Based View (RBV) of the firm emphasizes the role of internal resources and capabilities in driving competitive advantage and sustained performance (Madhani, 2010). Within this framework, real estate appraisers can be viewed as strategic resources that provide unique skills, knowledge, and expertise to businesses. Appraisers possess specialized capabilities in property valuation, market analysis, and risk assessment, which are valuable assets for businesses seeking to optimize their real estate investments and operations. By leveraging these resources effectively, businesses can enhance their competitiveness and create sustainable value in the real estate market (Abdul-Aziz et al., 2007; Liu et al., 2009).

Stakeholder Theory: Stakeholder theory posits that businesses are embedded within broader social and economic systems, and their actions impact various stakeholders, including employees, customers, suppliers, and communities (Parmar et al., 2010). Real estate appraisers serve as stakeholders in the real estate ecosystem, providing independent assessments of property

value and market conditions that influence decision-making by businesses and other stakeholders. By considering the interests and perspectives of multiple stakeholders, including appraisers, businesses can make more informed and socially responsible real estate decisions that align with broader societal goals and values (Poon et al., 2011; Kerscher, 2015).

Role of Real Estate Appraisers as Strategic Resources

Building upon the RBV and stakeholder theory, real estate appraisers can be conceptualized as strategic resources that contribute to competitive advantage and organizational performance. As specialized experts in property valuation and market analysis, appraisers offer unique capabilities that enable businesses to assess and manage real estate-related risks, identify investment opportunities, and optimize portfolio performance. By leveraging the expertise of appraisers strategically, businesses can enhance their decision-making processes, mitigate uncertainties, and achieve their strategic objectives in the dynamic real estate market. Real estate appraisers play a crucial role in shaping business strategy by providing valuable insights and recommendations based on their expertise in property valuation and market analysis (Yang et al., 2015). From informing investment decisions to supporting risk management and financial reporting, appraisers contribute to various aspects of strategic planning and execution in businesses. By integrating appraiser perspectives into strategic decision-making processes, businesses can enhance their ability to adapt to changing market conditions, capitalize on opportunities, and achieve sustainable growth in the real estate sector (Baffour Awuah et al., 2017; Doszyń, 2021).

Strategic Functions of Real Estate Appraisers

Real estate appraisers assist businesses in assessing and mitigating risks associated with real estate investments. Through comprehensive property valuations and market analysis, appraisers identify potential risks, such as market fluctuations, regulatory changes, or property-specific factors, and provide recommendations for risk mitigation strategies (Uchehara et al., 2020; Gupta and Newell, 2021). By understanding the risks inherent in their real estate holdings, businesses can make informed decisions to protect their investments and minimize potential losses. Appraisers play a critical role in financial reporting and compliance by providing accurate and reliable valuations of real estate assets. In accordance with accounting standards and regulatory requirements, businesses must report the fair market value of their real estate holdings in financial statements and disclosures. Real estate appraisers ensure compliance with these standards by conducting thorough appraisals based on established methodologies and industry best practices. Their expertise in valuation techniques and market analysis enables businesses to meet regulatory requirements and provide stakeholders with transparent and reliable financial information.

Real estate appraisers support businesses in evaluating real estate investment opportunities and maximizing returns (Mäki, 2020). By analyzing factors such as property value, rental income, operating expenses, and market

trends, appraisers assess the financial viability and potential risks of investment properties. Through detailed investment analysis, businesses can make informed decisions about acquiring, disposing of, or holding real estate assets, thereby optimizing their investment portfolios and achieving their financial objectives. Appraisers assist businesses in optimizing their real estate portfolios by identifying opportunities for value creation and risk mitigation (Żróbek et al., 2020; Ayodele, 2022). Through portfolio analysis and performance evaluation, appraisers assess the strengths and weaknesses of existing holdings, identify underperforming assets, and recommend strategies for portfolio optimization. By aligning real estate investments with business objectives and market dynamics, appraisers help businesses maximize portfolio value, enhance asset diversification, and mitigate portfolio-level risks (Tajani et al., 2020).

Real estate appraisers provide businesses with valuable insights into market trends, dynamics, and competitive factors that influence real estate decision-making (Robin, 2022). By monitoring market conditions, analyzing comparable sales data, and forecasting future trends, appraisers offer strategic intelligence that enables businesses to anticipate opportunities and risks in the real estate market. Through market intelligence, businesses can make proactive decisions to capitalize on emerging trends, adjust their strategies in response to market shifts, and maintain a competitive edge in the dynamic real estate landscape.

Real Estate Appraisers and Organizational Agility

The real estate market is characterized by dynamic and often unpredictable trends, including changes in supply and demand, economic conditions, and regulatory environments. In this context, organizational agility—the ability to respond quickly and effectively to changing market conditions—is essential for businesses to maintain resilience and competitive advantage (Ibrahim and Hassanain, 2022). Real estate appraisers play a critical role in supporting organizational agility by providing timely and accurate insights into market dynamics, enabling businesses to adapt their strategies and operations in response to changing market conditions.

Appraisers contribute to organizational agility by providing valuable market intelligence, risk assessments, and strategic recommendations that inform adaptation strategies (Wanxin, 2023). Through proactive monitoring of market trends, appraisers help businesses anticipate changes and identify opportunities for growth or risk mitigation. By leveraging appraiser insights, businesses can adjust their real estate strategies, optimize resource allocation, and seize strategic opportunities in the evolving market landscape. Real estate appraisers enable businesses to gain a competitive advantage by leveraging their appraisal insights to differentiate themselves in the marketplace. By incorporating appraiser recommendations into their strategic decision-making processes, businesses can develop innovative real estate strategies, optimize asset utilization, and enhance customer value propositions. Appraisers provide businesses with a unique source of competitive intelligence that enables them to

anticipate market trends, outmaneuver competitors, and maintain leadership positions in the real estate sector.

Technological Integration in Real Estate Appraisal

Technological advancements, such as Automated Valuation Models (AVMs), have revolutionized the real estate appraisal process by enabling automated property valuations based on algorithms and data analytics (Glumac and Des Rosiers, 2021). AVMs leverage vast amounts of property data, including sales transactions, market trends, and property characteristics, to generate fast and cost-effective property valuations. By automating routine valuation tasks, AVMs enhance appraisal efficiency, reduce turnaround times, and lower appraisal costs for businesses (Kok et al., 2017; Renigier-Bilozor et al., 2019).

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technology provides powerful tools for spatial analysis, mapping, and visualization of real estate data (De Toro et al., 2020). GIS enables real estate appraisers to analyze spatial relationships, identify spatial patterns, and visualize geographic trends that influence property values (Kucklick et al., 2021). By integrating GIS technology into their appraisal processes, appraisers can enhance their understanding of local market dynamics, assess property locations more effectively, and provide more accurate valuations to businesses (Zysk et al., 2020).

While technological advancements have transformed the real estate appraisal landscape, human expertise remains indispensable in ensuring accurate and reliable property valuations (Jebur, 2021). Real estate appraisers bring specialized knowledge, judgment, and experience to the appraisal process, enabling them to assess complex factors and nuances that may not be captured by automated algorithms alone. By balancing technological advancements with human expertise, businesses can leverage the strengths of both approaches to optimize appraisal outcomes, mitigate risks, and make informed real estate decisions

DISCUSSION

In delving into the strategic significance of real estate appraisers for businesses, especially within the unique context of Saudi Arabia, several crucial insights emerge that warrant deeper exploration. Firstly, it's paramount to acknowledge the foundational role of the real estate sector in driving economic prosperity, not just locally but also on a global scale. This sector acts as a fundamental pillar of economic health, serving as a barometer for overall economic vitality, stimulating investment, fostering job creation, and catalyzing infrastructural development.

Within this broader economic landscape, real estate appraisers emerge as pivotal actors, wielding significant influence over strategic decision-making processes and value creation initiatives for businesses. These professionals serve as conduits of indispensable insights into market dynamics, risk assessments, and strategic recommendations, empowering businesses to formulate adaptive strategies that respond effectively to evolving market

conditions. Their role extends beyond mere valuation; they are strategic advisors guiding businesses through the intricacies of the real estate landscape, enabling them to capitalize on opportunities and mitigate risks effectively. Real estate assets are fundamental components of businesses, serving as operational spaces, investment vehicles, and collateral for financing. The valuation and management of these assets are critical for businesses to make informed decisions and optimize their strategic objectives. Real estate appraisers play a pivotal role in this process by providing expertise in property valuation and market analysis (Yang et al., 2015; Alateeg and Alhammadi, 2023; 2024). In recent years, the significance of real estate appraisers has grown, reflecting the increasing complexity and dynamism of the real estate market (Maliene et al., 2010; Al-Tit et al., 2022; Al-Ayed, 2024). Factors such as globalization, technological advancements, and regulatory changes have heightened the demand for skilled appraisers who can navigate these challenges and provide reliable insights to businesses (Baffour Awuah et al., 2017; Al-Ayed and Al-Tit, 2024).

However, despite the accelerated growth witnessed in the Saudi Arabian real estate market, challenges persist, posing hurdles to optimal valuation practices (Warren-Myers, 2012). Foremost among these challenges is the absence of standardized valuation methodologies and professional frameworks, which undermine transparency and reliability in the appraisal process (Ramsey, 2004; Abidoye and Chan, 2016). Additionally, the reliance on subjective opinions and traditional valuation methods further complicates the landscape, raising questions about the accuracy and fairness of assessments. Amidst these challenges lie opportunities for innovation and advancement, particularly through technological integration. Automated Valuation Models (AVMs) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) hold promise in revolutionizing appraisal practices, enhancing efficiency, and bolstering accuracy. By embracing these technological tools, businesses can streamline their valuation processes, minimize errors, and gain a competitive edge in the market (Wofford et al., 2011; Doszyń, 2021).

Looking ahead, businesses must recognize the imperative of integrating appraiser insights into their strategic decision-making processes. This entails not only optimizing resource allocation and investment strategies but also prioritizing continuous professional development to stay abreast of evolving valuation methodologies and industry best practices. Collaboration and knowledge-sharing among stakeholders are essential for fostering a culture of professionalism and transparency within the real estate appraisal profession.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The real estate sector in Saudi Arabia holds significant importance, serving as a key driver of economic growth and development. The rapid urbanization witnessed in the country, fueled by factors such as population growth, governmental policies, and economic mobility, has led to a surge in real estate activity and attracted numerous individuals and institutions to enter the market. This increased interest has prompted the establishment of the Saudi

Authority for Accredited Valuers, highlighting the growing recognition of the need for standardized and professional real estate valuation processes. However, despite the accelerated movement in the real estate market, there remains a critical gap in the sector: the absence of comprehensive scientific studies and methodologies for real estate valuation, particularly from the perspectives of urban and architectural planning. Presently, the valuation process relies heavily on subjective opinions and traditional methods, raising concerns about transparency and accuracy. Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort to enhance the professionalism and transparency of the real estate valuation industry in Saudi Arabia. Establishing standardized professional frameworks and guidelines for real estate valuation would not only instill confidence among financiers, investors, and buyers but also ensure a fair and transparent assessment of property prices. Moreover, investing in research and education in the field of real estate valuation, with a focus on urban and architectural planning, is essential to bridge the existing knowledge gap and drive innovation in the sector.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

The real estate appraisal profession is continually evolving in response to technological advancements, regulatory changes, and market dynamics. Emerging trends such as blockchain technology, big data analytics, and sustainable valuation practices are reshaping the appraisal landscape and presenting new opportunities and challenges for businesses (Garcia-Teruel, 2020; Saari et al., 2022; Alateeg et al., 2024). By staying abreast of these emerging trends, businesses can anticipate future developments and position themselves strategically to adapt and thrive in the evolving real estate market (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019).

Despite advancements in real estate appraisal theory and practice, several areas remain ripe for further research. Topics such as the impact of technological integration on appraisal accuracy, the role of appraisers in sustainable real estate practices, and the effectiveness of alternative valuation methods warrant deeper investigation. By addressing these research gaps, scholars can advance understanding of the strategic importance of real estate appraisers and contribute to the ongoing evolution of the real estate appraisal profession.

The insights derived from this paper have practical implications for businesses seeking to leverage the expertise of real estate appraisers effectively. Businesses can enhance their strategic decision-making processes by integrating appraiser insights into their real estate strategies, investment decisions, and risk management practices. Moreover, businesses can invest in continuous professional development and collaboration with appraisers to enhance appraisal capabilities, optimize real estate investments, and achieve their strategic objectives in the dynamic real estate market.

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